

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Traore**FIRST NAME:** Mamadou Boussanga**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 8%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with a page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. How to avoid plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34)
2. Writing a good essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-8)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13)
4. Differences between US and UK English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25)
5. Understand what a style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41-42)
6. Usage of Zotero (Cleenewerck 2016)

KEY ELEMENTS TO KNOW ABOUT ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK

1)INTRODUCTION

At Euclid University, during the first period, every student interacts with various materials such as (textbooks/PDFs and videos. From reading and studying those materials (textbook/PDF and videos as assigned), the student must write a response paper (RP) according to standard EUCLID guidelines. This assignment is open, where I shall identify, reference, and personally interact with at least 5-7 key concepts. In that line, I am writing this response paper to summarize critical points studied from EUCLID's ACA-401 Coursepack based on acceptable and academic standard paper writing. These topics will include the following issues: how to avoid plagiarism, writing a good essay, some rules of thumb for writing a paper, differences between us and UK English, understanding a style guide, and usage of Zotero.

2) HOW TO AVOID PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using or taking someone else's words or ideas from any source without crediting the author, for example, quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet. Having someone write a paper for you, putting your name on it, and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). In academic writing, I must put references or citations and provide sources of where I obtain the information for my readers to avoid plagiarism.

Plagiarism could be considered unethical, and it is a serious academic offense that can lead to severe consequences such as loss of reputation and credibility. Plagiarism can negatively affect your future career, regardless of whether it was intentional.

When you write an academic paper, you build upon the work of others and use various credible sources for information and evidence. Plagiarism can be avoided by taking into consideration the following points (George 2021):

- Keeping track of the sources you consult in your research,
- Paraphrasing or quoting from your sources (by using a paraphrasing tool and adding your ideas),
- Crediting the original author in an in-text citation and your reference list, and
- Use a plagiarism checker before you submit.

This particular unit taught me various elements that will improve my academic writing skills. Among those, we have how to cite and what it means quotation and citation (in-text citation and list of works cited). Now, I am well equipped on how to cite and use in-text citations using the Chicago style/Turabian with the author's last name, date, and page number, as well as references/bibliography.

3) WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

There are many ways to write an essay, but we will focus on academic papers for this exercise.

Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic writing include research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference papers; books or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). For writing an academic essay, you should start as early as possible and get enough time to read, write, and research your topic. Secondly, it is crucial to define

questions and analysis of tasks, and when finding out about the subject, it is essential to analyze and present the answer to the question. Developing a plan and putting down your initial ideas is critical and can help guide your research and address any question or type of information to use.

I was well equipped with knowledge and evidence on developing a thesis and answering questions through reading and researching, which are also the foundation for any relevant research. While reading, you should always take notes by underlining or highlighting relevant information, which you can use later.

In good essay writing, you should also think about structuring and organizing your idea, and for that, the following steps could be taken into consideration (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8):

- Decide on a possible answer to the question,
- Select the information you will use to answer the question,
- Keep looking at your notes to support your answer through selected evidence,
- Decide which points you will discuss and in which order, and
- Write the above points in a sketch form, as this will be your essay plan.

Finally, good essay writing needs to initiate a preliminary draft, which can be reviewed and adjusted. Having a draft document developed could also drive you toward successful essay writing. The essay plan could include an introduction, a body, and a conclusion.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

In that section, I have learned some critical suggestions for writing essays. For example, you can announce the central thesis of your paper at the starting point, especially in the first paragraph. Using words such as "I will argue that" If you do not have a thesis, getting one is highly suggested (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13).

Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper require a writer to stay focused and critically assess relevant aspects of the theories, such as the thesis of your paper, stated near the beginning. You should write with clarity and make your writing very impactful and lively. When writing, do not use every sentence with the subject. Moreover, stay away from passive constructions: instead of "The wheel was invented by Joe," why not: "Joe invented the wheel" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13).

5) DIFFERENCES BETWEEN US AND UK ENGLISH

The differences between US and UK English will be covered in that section. American and British English all come from the same sources and, therefore, are closer than different, especially in the scientific and academic world. Despite their similarity, there are specific differences in spelling and pronunciation. The following general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) each have their sociolects value are the concert example (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25).

6) UNDERSTAND WHAT A STYLE GUIDE

EUCLID accepts various international styles for developing academic papers, such as the WHO style, but the Chicago Rules (Turabian) is the most recommended. In addition to that, American English is also preferred, but I can use both versions, which are also accepted (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41).

As a writer, you must use a consistent writing style that helps document your approach. Certain types of writing, such as technical writing, business or business writing, journalism, and web writing, generally rely on style guides. To do this in each case, the author will endeavor to ensure consistency. Authors' contribution based on the published guidelines often gives an impersonal character that does not highlight the style of the writer but the publication, company, or other associated web link. The consistency of final publication with multi-authored companies often depends on a recommended or published style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). Freelance writers always need a style guide for their writing, the reason why it is noted in the ACA-401 Coursepack.

“Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type. It is important that, as a freelancer, you can demonstrate an ability to follow a prescribed style, but equally that you can learn and record what your customers prefer from their comments” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 42).

A style guide is essential when writing a specific document for that particular unit. Using a style guide could help increase the coherence of your writing and the quality.

7) USAGE OF ZETERO

For the development of an academic document, the author must ensure to give the references of all the data sources used in the context of his work, the bibliography, citation, etc. Software programs such as Zotero are used to provide connections, quotations, and bibliography, particularly in this work's context. Zotero is an open-access, easy-to-use reference management tool that serves as your personal research assistant and helps you collect, organize, cite, and share your research sources. I used Zotero when writing a Response Paper and found it very easy to gather citation records for non-PDF content.

Zotero's single-click capture works with more databases, catalogs, and websites. The other advantages' of Zotero are the following: reasonably easy to learn; all features come with the free version; all software upgrades are free; and collaborative group libraries.

8)CONCLUSION

I found this integrated course pack developed by EUCLID and some presentations, such as Zotero, very critical tools to help students and other writers meet the internationally recognized standard paper writing. This course pack taught me different methods for my academic endeavor, such as a style guide, avoiding plagiarism, and the difference between UK and US English in pronunciation and spelling.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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George, Tegan. 2021. "How to Avoid Plagiarism | Tips on Citing Sources." Accessed October 10, 2021. <https://www.scribbr.com/plagiarism/how-to-avoid-plagiarism/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.